

(RTD), photothermal units (PTU), and heliothermal units (HTU)—were derived for correlation and regression studies. Variations were observed in different parameters, not only because of genotype characters and seasonal influence but also because of the interaction between them. Most floral characters were better expressed in the summer season (February to May) than in the samba season (October to January).

Among the parental lines, the A lines recorded higher values for days to first flowering, 50% flowering, duration of flowering in a panicle, period of anthesis, stigma exertion, and productive tillers than their respective maintainers. Correlation studies with days to first flowering, duration of flowering in a panicle, and panicle exertion proved significant in all the parents except AS 89044. All the heat unit concepts showed a significant correlation for IR10198-66-2R. Among the heat unit concepts, HTU played a limited role in altering floral characters. Regression equations were fitted to predict the flowering behavior of these parental lines. These studies will be useful in identifying parental lines with stability against seasonal influences. Staggered sowing of B/R lines based on the season of seed production can be done based on such results. ■

Determining seeding intervals of parents in hybrid rice seed production

A.H. Krishnamurthy, B.V. Chandra, R.M. Radhakrishna, and S. Lingaraju, Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya 571405, Karnataka, India

For hybrid seed production, two parents—a cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line (female) and restorer (male) lines—are planted in alternate rows. Similarly, to multiply CMS lines, the CMS and maintainer lines are planted in alternate rows. Simultaneous flowering in both male and female lines is highly essential for seed set.

Flowering duration in the male and female lines differs, and, therefore, there will not be any synchrony in flowering of the male and female lines if they are sown on the same day. Parental lines differing in their growth duration can be sown on different days in nursery beds so that they can reach flowering at the same time in the main field. To determine the seeding interval of the parents of KRH2 and CMS line IR58025A, studies were conducted in the 1995 wet season. IR58025A flowered in 90 d whereas its maintainer, IR58025B, flowered in 85 d. KMR-3R, the restorer parent of KRH2, flowered in 98 d. Therefore, the growth duration difference between IR58025A and KMR-3R was 8 d. But maintainer line IR58025B flowered 5 d earlier than the A line. The leaves on the main culm in each of the parents were counted. The parents, IR58025A, IR58025B, and KMR-3, produced 15, 14, and 16 leaves at flowering, respectively.

The results indicated that IR58025B should be sown 5 d after sowing IR58025A or when IR58025A produces one leaf in the nursery for CMS multiplication. For KRH2 hybrid seed production, IR58025A should be sown 8 d after sowing restorer line KMR-3R or when the restorer line produces 1.4 leaves in the nursery. ■

Adjusting flowering of a CMS line in hybrid rice seed production

S. Lingaraju, B.V. Chandra, V. Bhaskar, and S. Gangadhariah, Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya 571405, Karnataka, India

Seed production of hybrids, unlike that of inbred varieties, involves difficult procedures. In hybrid rice seed production, two parents—a cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line (female) and restorer line (male)—are grown in alternate fixed row ratios, one after the other. The female line, which is male sterile, receives pollen from the male, which is fertile and set the seed. Therefore, it is

essential that both male and female parents flower at the same time. Techniques such as the leaf count method and growth duration difference method are used for the differential seeding of male and female parents. Flowering in male and female parents often fails to synchronize because of environmental conditions. In China, where hybrid seed is produced on a large scale, several techniques have been adopted to synchronize flowering at the early stages of panicle development.

Because seed growers in Karnataka found it difficult to identify the early stages of panicle development, we attempted to develop simple techniques that could be adopted at the later stages of panicle development (at the half and full boot leaf stage). IR58025A was the common CMS line used for different hybrids in Karnataka. Adjustment of flowering in this line was studied during the 1995 wet season. Techniques such as spraying gibberellic acid (GA_3) and urea and applying potash, phosphorus, and urea to the base of plants were tried.

The results indicated that the above treatments at the half boot leaf stage had no effect on flowering. At the full boot leaf stage, however, a GA_3 spray at 60 ppm advanced 50% flowering by 3 d and full flowering by 5 d. The total duration of flowering was reduced by 5 d. Applying urea at 20 kg ha⁻¹ to the base of plants at the full boot leaf stage delayed both 50 and 100% flowering by 2 d. Similarly, the total duration of flowering also increased by 2 d. Applying phosphorus at the rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ at the full boot leaf stage delayed 50 and 100% flowering by 2 d, but flowering duration decreased by 3 d. Therefore, by spraying GA_3 at 60 ppm at the full boot leaf stage, we can advance flowering in CMS line IR58025A. With an application of urea or phosphorus at 20 kg ha⁻¹, flowering can be delayed, when necessary, by 2 d in CMS line IR58025A. This method can be used to synchronize flowering adequately. ■